

Original article

UNVEILING KEY DETERMINANTS OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING AMONG EUROPEAN OLDER ADULTS: A MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH

Alexandra-Cristina SÎRBU¹

¹Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași, 0009-0002-8268-9026

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Abstract: Subjective well-being has become a central focus in aging research, reflecting the interplay between psychological, social, and economic factors in later life. This study investigates the key determinants of subjective well-being among older adults in Europe, utilizing data from the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) waves 7–9. By integrating penalized regression models (Lasso and Ridge) with machine learning techniques such as Gradient Boosting, the analysis offers a comprehensive perspective on the factors shaping life satisfaction. The results emphasize the essential role of mental health—particularly depression—as the most significant predictor of well-being, followed by social relationships and financial security. Notably, subjective financial stability exerts a stronger influence on well-being than actual income, highlighting the psychological dimensions of financial security. While aging itself is associated with a modest increase in well-being, physical health decline and functional limitations negatively impact life satisfaction, used as measure of subjective well-being. The use of machine learning enhances the ability to detect complex interactions between predictors, providing deeper insights beyond traditional statistical methods. These findings underscore the need for targeted policy interventions that prioritize mental health support, social inclusion, and financial resilience to promote well-being in aging populations.

Keywords: Subjective Well-Being, SHARE, Ageing, Machine Learning

JEL classification: I31, C55

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1. Introduction

In economics, it is traditionally assumed that individuals aim to maximize their utility, a concept encompassing pleasure, satisfaction, preferences, and well-being while making decisions under limited resources (Mas-Colell et al., 1995). Extending this idea, well-being has become an increasingly central focus in research, particularly in the context of demographic aging. The relevance of studying well-being is further underscored by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals for 2030, which emphasize health and well-being as critical policy priorities, especially in response to aging populations and their associated challenges (United Nations, 2015).

Expanding on this economic foundation, well-being research has moved beyond traditional indicators such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP) to incorporate broader, multidimensional assessments. Criticisms such as those of Kennedy (1968), who argued that GDP “measures everything in short, except that which makes life worthwhile” highlighted the limitations of relying solely on economic metrics. This perspective paved the way for more comprehensive measures of well-being that integrate both objective and subjective aspects of life, recognizing that financial prosperity alone does not equate to life satisfaction (Costanza et al., 2014; Kahneman et al., 2004). While macroeconomic analyses provide valuable insights into national well-being trends, they can obscure individual-level variations and fail to capture the nuances of personal experiences. As Steptoe et al. (2015) argue, policies based purely on macroeconomic data may be inadequate for addressing the well-being needs of specific subpopulations, particularly older adults.

To address these limitations, researchers have increasingly emphasized an individual-level approach, enabling a more detailed analysis of factors such as physical and mental health, financial security, social relationships,

¹ cristina.sirbu@uaic.ro

and self-esteem, which are essential for understanding well-being at a personal level. Health, in particular, has been consistently identified as a major determinant, with both physical and mental health conditions playing a significant role in shaping well-being (Dolan et al., 2008; Deaton, 2008; Kamkary & Shokrzadeh, 2012). Additionally, social relationships, including marital status and self-esteem, have been linked to variations in life satisfaction, highlighting the importance of interpersonal connections and psychological traits in shaping well-being outcomes (Steel et al., 2008; Ghaedi et al., 2010; Lyubomirsky et al., 2005; Burger et al., 2020).

These factors are essential for understanding what contributes to a fulfilling and satisfying life and are particularly relevant in evaluating the well-being of older adults. By focusing on the diverse individual experiences of aging populations, our research addresses the necessity of understanding the interplay between material and social conditions and how they shape well-being outcomes.

While these findings provide useful insights, most studies rely on regression-based models that assume linear relationships between predictors and well-being outcomes, potentially overlooking more complex patterns. In response, researchers have increasingly turned to machine learning techniques that offer greater flexibility in capturing nonlinear relationships and interdependencies (Bolier et al., 2013; Diener et al., 2018). Modern analytical approaches allow for a more data-driven identification of key predictors, improving accuracy and addressing limitations such as multicollinearity and overfitting. However, applications of machine learning in this field remain limited, particularly in studies focused on older adults. Given the aging population and the distinct factors influencing well-being in later life, further exploration using advanced analytical techniques is warranted.

To address these challenges, this study applies both regularized regression methods, such as Lasso and Ridge, and ensemble-based machine learning techniques, as Gradient Boosting, to systematically assess the key predictors of subjective well-being. While regression methods remain widely used for estimating associations between variables, modern machine learning techniques provide a more flexible framework that allows for the detection of nonlinear relationships and complex interactions. By leveraging these complementary approaches, this study aims to provide a more nuanced understanding of the factors shaping well-being in later life.

Given the complexity of well-being, a key distinction in research is between subjective well-being (SWB) and objective well-being. Objective well-being relies on external indicators such as income, education, and health status, whereas SWB captures individuals' cognitive and emotional evaluations of their lives, offering a more personal perspective on well-being. While objective well-being is measured through external indicators such as income, education, and health status, SWB captures individuals' cognitive and emotional evaluations of their lives, reflecting their perceived quality of life. Due to the inherently personal nature of well-being, subjective measures are increasingly recognized as essential for understanding life satisfaction and happiness (Diener, 1984; OECD, 2013). This study focuses on subjective well-being, acknowledging its significance in complementing traditional economic and social indicators to provide a more holistic understanding of well-being among older adults.

To examine these aspects in depth, this study utilizes data from the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), specifically waves 7, 8, and 9 which provide comprehensive and up-to-date information on aging populations across multiple European countries (SHARE-ERIC, 2024a, 2024b, 2024c). By integrating multiple analytical approaches, this study seeks to systematically investigate:

1. Which factors, encompassing various dimensions of human life, emerge as the most significant predictors of subjective well-being among adults aged 50 and above in Europe?
2. Among the key predictors identified, which exert the most substantial influence on subjective well-being within the studied population?

The structure of this paper is as follows. The next section outlines the key factors influencing subjective well-being, followed by a description of the dataset and the methodological approach. The subsequent section presents and interprets the empirical findings, and the paper concludes with a Discussion & Conclusions section that synthesizes the key findings and their implications.

2. Literature review

The extensive body of literature on subjective well-being (SWB) has explored a wide range of determinants, making it challenging to provide an exhaustive overview of all influencing factors. While well-being can be examined from both subjective and objective perspectives, research often distinguishes between macro-level and micro-level determinants. National-level influences such as economic prosperity, sociocultural conditions, and political structures contribute to broader well-being trends, yet individual-level factors play a more direct role in shaping personal life satisfaction. Given this, our study focuses on the micro-level determinants of well-being, particularly those that affect older adults in Europe. Key aspects such as physical and mental health, social relationships, and financial stability are central to understanding how well-being is experienced and how it can be improved among aging populations.

Among the various factors influencing subjective well-being, health has been consistently identified as one of the strongest predictors of well-being, with both physical and mental health playing an important role in shaping life satisfaction. Empirical studies have shown that individuals with chronic illnesses and poor health status tend to report lower subjective well-being (Dolan et al., 2008; Kamkary & Shokrzadeh, 2012). The relationship is bidirectional, as poor well-being can also contribute to health deterioration. Mental health conditions, particularly depression and anxiety, have been found to have an even stronger impact on well-being than physical ailments, affecting emotional stability and daily functioning (Diener et al., 1999; Binder & Coad, 2011; Cubí-Mollá et al., 2014). Some research suggests that self-reported health measures may be more strongly correlated with well-being than clinically assessed health conditions (Larson, 1978; Okun et al., 1984).

Personality traits have also been extensively studied in relation to well-being, with findings indicating that extraversion and agreeableness are positively associated with life satisfaction, while neuroticism has a strong negative effect (DeNeve & Cooper, 1998; Steel et al., 2008). High self-esteem, optimism, and emotional intelligence have been linked to greater resilience and higher well-being (Lyubomirsky et al., 2006; Diener et al., 1995; Lench, 2011). Neuroticism, on the other hand, has been shown to contribute to emotional instability and heightened sensitivity to negative experiences (Rusting & Larsen, 1997; Eid & Larsen, 2008). Furthermore, self-perception, particularly self-esteem, has been highlighted as a significant factor influencing well-being, with individuals who perceive themselves positively reporting greater life satisfaction (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005; Diener, 2009).

Demographic factors such as age, gender, and marital status also play important roles in well-being. The relationship between age and happiness has been described as U-shaped, with lower levels of well-being in middle adulthood and higher levels among younger and older individuals (Graham & Pozuelo, 2017; Schwandt, 2016). The mechanisms behind this trend may include life course adaptations, emotional regulation, and shifting priorities. Gender differences in well-being have produced mixed findings, as studies indicate that while women may experience more intense positive and negative emotions, overall life satisfaction levels do not differ significantly between genders (Tesch-Römer et al., 2008; Nasser & Fakhroo, 2021). Marital status has been positively linked to well-being, with married individuals often reporting higher life satisfaction than their unmarried counterparts (Dolan et al., 2008; Kahneman & Deaton, 2010). However, relationship quality has been shown to be more important than marital status itself, as individuals in high-conflict marriages do not necessarily benefit from marriage in terms of well-being (Stutzer & Frey, 2004).

Economic determinants such as income and employment status remain central to subjective well-being research. The Easterlin Paradox suggests that while higher income is associated with greater life satisfaction, its marginal effect diminishes once basic needs are met (Easterlin, 1974; Kahneman & Deaton, 2010). Financial stability, rather than absolute income, appears to be more strongly associated with well-being (Clark et al., 2008). Unemployment has been consistently linked to lower life satisfaction, not only due to financial insecurity but also due to the psychological impact of losing a sense of purpose and social interaction (Jahoda, 1982; Knabe et al., 2010). Research indicates that secure employment and job quality contribute significantly to life satisfaction, while job-related stress can offset potential benefits (Bryson & MacKerron, 2017; Axelrad et al., 2020).

Social relationships and engagement in community life are critical for subjective well-being. Individuals with strong social networks and supportive relationships tend to experience higher levels of life satisfaction (Cornwell et al., 2008; Haslam et al., 2008). Studies have found that both the frequency and quality of social interactions contribute to well-being, particularly among older adults who may face increased risks of isolation (Tani et al., 2022). Participation in community activities, volunteering, and religious engagement have been associated with enhanced well-being due to their roles in fostering social integration and purpose (Ellison, 1991; Helliwell, 2006; O'Maoileidigh, 2022).

Education plays a complex role in well-being. While higher education levels are generally linked to greater life satisfaction due to increased economic opportunities and cognitive development, some studies suggest that highly educated individuals experience greater stress due to competitive job markets and high expectations (Clark, 2018; Nasser & Fakhroo, 2021). Education can also enhance well-being by improving social mobility and access to resources, but its effects may be mediated by other socioeconomic factors (Becker, 1964; Barysheva et al., 2018).

While much of the previous research mentioned has relied on traditional statistical methods to examine the relationship between well-being and its determinants, recent advances have incorporated machine learning (ML) techniques to enhance predictive accuracy and uncover complex interactions between factors. Studies such as those by Kaiser et al. (2022) have utilized ML models to explore the relationship between age and life satisfaction. Similarly, Prati (2022) applied machine learning to identify key correlates of quality of life among European adults aged 50 and older. Additionally, Collins et al. (2015) utilized supervised learning models to analyze data extracted from Facebook, demonstrating that social media activity can be used to predict life satisfaction and subjective well-

being. Their findings highlight the potential of digital footprints in assessing well-being, though challenges related to data representativeness and model interpretability remain.

Building upon these findings, recent applications of machine learning in well-being research have expanded to various populations and contexts, demonstrating the adaptability of these techniques across different datasets and demographic groups. For instance, research conducted in Turkey by Gias et al. (2023) has used ML techniques to detect anxiety states based on socio-economic data, highlighting the role of social and economic conditions in shaping mental well-being. Another study in Bangladesh by Siddiqua et al. (2023) introduced a hybrid depression assessment scale using deep learning, refining predictive models for mental health outcomes.

These advancements illustrate the growing potential of ML methodologies in subjective well-being research, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of well-being predictors beyond traditional statistical techniques. However, challenges such as model interpretability, generalizability across different populations, and the need for robust validation methods highlight the importance of continued refinement in this field.

3. Data and methodology

3.1. Presentation of the dataset

The data used in this study come from the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), specifically waves 7–9 (SHARE-ERIC, 2024a, 2024b, 2024c). SHARE is a multidisciplinary, biannual study launched in 2004 that investigates the health, socio-economic status, and social networks of individuals aged 50 and above across Europe, providing a comprehensive perspective on ageing.

For this analysis, the dependent variable is life satisfaction, which serves as a proxy for subjective well-being. It is measured using the following survey question: *"On a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means completely dissatisfied and 10 means completely satisfied, how satisfied are you with your life?"*

The independent variables include a set of key predictors known to influence life satisfaction among older adults. These variables are selected based on previous research and are categorized into five broad dimensions:

- Demographic and socio-economic characteristics: Age, gender, marital status, education level, and financial situation.
- Health status: Self-reported physical and mental health, presence of chronic conditions, and limitations in daily activities.
- Social connections and participation: Frequency of social interactions, involvement in community activities, and perceived social support.
- Material well-being: Income level, housing conditions, and financial security.
- Psychological and personality traits: Measures related to optimism, resilience, and perceived control over life.

A detailed description of the independent variables, along with their possible values, is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Determinants of Subjective Well-Being Among Older Adults

Factor	Type of variable	Variable
Socio-demographic characteristics		
Gender	Qualitative (0. Male 1. Female)	gender_1
Age	Quantitative	age
Years of education	Quantitative	education
Marital status	Qualitative (1. Married and living with spouse; 2. Registered partnership; 3. Married, living separately from spouse; 4. Never married; 5. Divorced; 6. Widowed)	mstat1, mstat2, mstat3, mstat4, mstat5, mstat6
Employment status	Qualitative (1. Retired; 2. Employed or self-employed; 3. Unemployed; 4. Permanently ill or disabled; 5. Homemaker; 6. Other)	cjs1, cjs2, cjs3, cjs4, cjs5, cjs6
Area of residence	Qualitative (1. A big city; 2. The suburbs or outskirts of a big city; 3. A large town;	area1, area2, area3, area4, area5

	4. A small town; 5. A rural area or village)	
Age prevents from doing things	Qualitative (1. Often – 4. Never)	age_prevents
Health		
Number of chronic diseases	Quantitative	chronic
Limitations in daily activities	Qualitative (0. No; 1. Yes)	limitation
Mobility, arm function, fine motor limitations (number of limitations)	Quantitative	mobility
Seen/Talked to medical doctor (no.)	Quantitative	medical visits
EURO depression scale	Quantitative	eurod
Self-perceived health – US scale	Qualitative (0- Very good/excellent; 1- Less than very good)	health_perceived
Social networks and participation in social life		
Number of participations in social activities in the last year	Quantitative	activities
Satisfaction with social network	Quantitative	sn_satisf
Feel left out of things	Qualitative (1. Often; 2. Sometimes; 3. Rarely; 4. Never)	sent_exclz
Scale of social connectedness, a summary scale of the social network data (higher = higher connectedness)	Qualitative	sn_scale
Material standards		
Able to make ends meet	Qualitative (1. With great difficulty; 2. With some difficulty; 3. Fairly easily; 4. Easily)	income_FL
Inability to accomplish things for lack of money	Qualitative (1. Often; 2. Sometimes; 3. Rarely; 4. Never)	lack of money
Income member/month	Quantitative	member income
Personality traits		
Big Five – Neuroticism	Quantitative	neuroticism
Big Five – Extraversion	Quantitative	extraversion
Big Five – Agreeableness	Quantitative	agreeableness
Big Five – Conscientiousness	Quantitative	conscientiousness
Big Five – Openness	Quantitative	openness

Source: author's own processing

The final dataset includes 25,829 individuals, tracked across the three survey waves, resulting in a total of 77,487 observations. The study covers 25 European countries (excluding Portugal and the Netherlands but including Switzerland). Statistical analyses were conducted using Stata and R Studio, enabling efficient data handling and the application of advanced longitudinal analysis techniques.

3.2. Methodology

This study employs a structured machine learning approach to evaluate model performance, analyze feature importance, and optimize predictive accuracy. The methodology consists of three main components: performance evaluation, feature selection, and predictive modeling.

The first stage involves assessing model performance using standard statistical metrics, including Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2). These indicators provide a quantitative measure of prediction accuracy, where lower MAE, MSE, and RMSE values indicate lower prediction errors, and an R^2 value closer to 1 suggests a better fit of the model to the observed data.

To identify the most influential predictors, feature importance analysis is conducted through permutation importance and partial pseudo-effects (PPEs). Permutation importance (Breiman, 2001) quantifies the contribution of each predictor by randomly shuffling its values and measuring the corresponding increase in prediction error. A significant error increase suggests a high dependency on the given feature. To ensure statistical reliability, multiple permutations are performed on the response variable, generating a null importance distribution. This distribution is estimated using a probabilistic model, such as Gaussian, log-normal, or gamma distributions, with parameters determined via maximum likelihood estimation. If the distribution fit is ambiguous, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test is applied, or a non-parametric approach is used.

In addition, partial pseudo-effects (PPEs) are employed to examine the relationship between each predictor and the dependent variable while controlling for other influences. PPEs are computed by adjusting the predictor's values at critical distribution points (e.g., median, quantiles) and evaluating how these modifications impact model predictions. This approach provides a deeper understanding of variable interactions and their effects on the output.

For predictive modeling, this study applies two regularized regression methods—Lasso regression and Ridge regression—along with a more advanced ensemble learning technique, Gradient Boosting. Although Lasso and Ridge regression are often considered traditional statistical techniques, they are classified within machine learning as penalized regression models used in supervised learning. Unlike ensemble-based methods, these techniques focus on regularization, feature selection, and improving the stability of predictions rather than iteratively refining errors.

Lasso regression (Tibshirani, 1996) introduces an L1-norm penalty, which forces some regression coefficients to shrink to zero, effectively performing both regularization and automatic feature selection. The optimization function is:

$$\hat{\beta} = \arg \min_{\beta} (\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - X_i \beta)^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j|) \quad (1)$$

where y_i represents the observed response variable, X_i denotes the vector of predictor variables, β is the vector of regression coefficients, λ is the regularization parameter controlling the strength of penalization.

By imposing an absolute constraint on the regression coefficients, Lasso performs both regularization and variable selection. When λ increases, the model reduces the complexity by eliminating variables with minimal predictive power, yielding a sparse representation that retains only the most relevant predictors. This technique is particularly useful when dealing with high-dimensional datasets, as it simplifies the model while retaining only the most relevant predictors.

On the other hand, Ridge regression (Hoerl & Kennard, 1976) applies an L2-norm penalty, which prevents extreme coefficient values and enhances model stability in the presence of multicollinearity. Unlike Lasso, Ridge does not eliminate variables but instead distributes the penalty across all predictors. The optimization function is:

$$\hat{\beta} = \arg \min_{\beta} (\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - X_i \beta)^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^2) \quad (2)$$

where all terms retain the same definitions as in Lasso regression. Unlike Lasso, Ridge does not perform variable selection, but rather shrinks the magnitude of all coefficients, making it particularly effective in handling multicollinearity among predictors.

While Lasso is preferred for feature selection, Ridge regression is beneficial when all predictors contribute meaningful information to the model.

To enhance predictive accuracy, Gradient Boosting (Friedman, 2001) is implemented as an ensemble learning technique that sequentially builds models to correct residual errors from previous iterations. Unlike Lasso and Ridge regression, which apply penalization techniques to a single linear model, Gradient Boosting constructs a series of weak models that iteratively refine the predictions. Given a dataset with predictor variables X and a response variable y , the objective is to find a function $F(x)$ that minimizes a predefined loss function $F(y, F(x))$. The optimization process follows these steps:

- 1. Initialization:** The model starts with a constant function, often the mean of the response variable:

$$F_0(x) = \arg \min_{\gamma} \sum_{i=1}^n L(y_i, \gamma) \quad (3)$$

- 2. Gradient-based learning process:**

In each iteration m , the algorithm:

- Computes the pseudo-residuals, which represent the negative gradient of the loss function:

$$r_{im} = - \left[\frac{\partial L(y_i, F(x_i))}{\partial F(x_i)} \right]_{F=F_{m-1}} \quad (4)$$

- Fits a weak learner (a decision tree) to approximate these residuals:

$$h_m(x) \approx \arg \min_h \sum_{i=1}^n (r_{im} - h(x_i))^2 \quad (5)$$

- Updates the predictive function by incorporating the new model:

$$F_m(x) = F_{m-1}(x) + \beta h_m(x) \quad (6)$$

where β represents the learning rate, which controls the contribution of each new model to prevent overfitting. The key hyperparameters, including the number of trees (N_{trees}) and shrinkage parameter (β), are optimized through grid search.

3. Final model output: After M iterations, the final prediction is:

$$\hat{y} = F_m(x) \quad (7)$$

where M is the total number of boosting iterations.

To ensure model generalization and avoid overfitting, k-fold cross-validation (k=5) is applied. The dataset is initially divided into training (60%) and validation/test subsets (40%), ensuring that evaluation is performed on unseen data. The cross-validation process iteratively trains models on different data partitions, allowing for robust performance estimation.

Hyperparameter tuning is carried out using a grid search approach, systematically testing multiple configurations to identify the optimal combination of learning rate, tree depth, and other parameters. Model selection is based on minimizing RMSE while maximizing R^2 , ensuring both predictive accuracy and model interpretability.

After finalizing hyperparameter selection and model optimization, the model undergoes a final evaluation on the test set to verify its ability to generalize to new, unseen data. This step ensures that the model is not only accurate in its predictions but also adaptable and reliable in various application scenarios. This aspect is particularly important in domains such as subjective well-being analysis, where predictive robustness is essential for drawing meaningful insights.

By integrating both penalized regression models and ensemble learning, this methodological framework balances model simplicity, feature selection, and predictive power, providing a robust approach to evaluating relationships between variables and optimizing prediction accuracy.

4. Results

To identify key determinants of subjective well-being, we employed a Lasso regression model with 10-fold cross-validation and grid search optimization for the lambda parameter, ranging from 0.001 to 0.1. The optimal model selected based on the lowest RMSE (1.361) at lambda = 0.001, effectively balanced model complexity and predictive accuracy while mitigating overfitting. Lasso’s ability to shrink coefficients allowed for a precise selection of influential factors, with no predictors being eliminated (Figure 1). Performance was assessed through RMSE, MAE, and R-squared metrics, confirming the model’s robustness (Table 2). While the R-squared value remained modest, it highlighted the model’s capacity to reveal statistically significant relationships, aligning with the primary goal of social research—understanding the interplay between various life aspects rather than achieving perfect prediction (Ozili, 2023).

Ridge regression, optimized at lambda = 0.056, also exhibited strong generalization capabilities, stabilizing coefficient estimates under high multicollinearity. Unlike Lasso, Ridge retained all predictors but penalized their impact, reducing overfitting while preserving informative relationships. Similar RMSE and MAE values across training, validation, and test sets suggested no significant overfitting, with R-squared values not exceeding 32% (Table 2).

Gradient Boosting was evaluated using an optimal configuration of 1000 trees, a learning rate of 0.05, interaction depth of 5, a minimum of 20 observations per node, and a subsampling rate of 0.75. This model demonstrated strong predictive consistency across training, validation, and test sets, with minor RMSE and MAE

variations indicating minimal overfitting (Table 2). However, R-squared values remained below 40%, suggesting that additional unobserved factors contribute to subjective well-being. While predictive power was limited, the model effectively identified meaningful relationships between variables, reinforcing the importance of further exploration into well-being determinants.

Table 2: Comparison of the efficiency of LASSO and Ridge Regression methods and the Gradient Boosting algorithm in modelling the determinants of subjective well-being.

Dataset	Indicator	LASSO	RIDGE	GRADIENT BOOSTING
		$\lambda=0.001$	$\lambda=0.056$	
Training set	MAE	1,0276	1,0278	0,9803
	RMSE	1,3605	1,3606	1,2951
	R ²	0,3290	0,3289	0,3931
Validation set	MAE	1,0301	1,0302	1,0115
	RMSE	1,3664	1,3667	1,3489
	R ²	0,3256	0,3254	0,3428
Test set	MAE	1,0304	1,0306	1,0169
	RMSE	1,3625	1,3628	1,3506
	R ²	0,3209	0,3207	0,3328

Source: Table based on SHARE w7-8-9

Key determinants of subjective well-being were identified, spanning social, financial, health, and psychological dimensions. The regression analysis (Figure 1) identified key factors influencing subjective well-being, with the sense of exclusion showing a significant impact. Treated as an ordinal variable, sentiment of exclusion was analyzed using linear, quadratic, and cubic transformations. The results indicate a strong linear relationship—lower exclusion correlates with higher well-being—while nonlinear effects were not significant, suggesting a stable and direct influence.

Financial security also played a significant role, with perceived financial stability having a stronger impact on well-being than actual household income. This highlights the importance of subjective financial control. The ability to manage expenses until the end of the month and the absence of financial constraints positively influenced well-being, with linear effects best capturing these relationships.

Employment status significantly affected well-being, with unemployment having a pronounced negative effect (Figure 1). Unlike retirement, which is often planned and expected, unemployment is associated with social stigma and loss of identity. Similarly, depression (measured by the Euro-D scale) and poor self-rated health had strong negative effects, reinforcing the importance of mental health interventions.

Social relationships emerged as a key determinant of well-being. Higher satisfaction in social interactions was significantly linked to increased well-being, emphasizing the role of emotional support and social belonging. Personality traits also influenced life satisfaction, with extraversion and openness to experience positively associated, while neuroticism had a negative effect.

Figure 1: Determinants of subjective well-being: comparative analysis of coefficients by Lasso and Ridge regression

Source: Graph based on SHARE w7-8-9

Model dependencies were further analyzed through permutation importance (Figure 2), where random alterations in variable values demonstrated their effect on model performance. Additionally, pseudo-partial effects were estimated, revealing the specific contribution of each variable to well-being. Continuous and ordinal variables were evaluated at different quantiles, while binary variables were assessed through their transition from 0 to 1.

The permutation importance analysis (Figure 2) highlights depression (Euro-D scale) and social network satisfaction as the most influential factors in subjective well-being. These findings emphasize the profound impact of mental health and social support on individuals’ overall well-being. Depression, a key indicator of mental health, negatively affects daily functioning and life quality, while social support provides essential emotional and practical resources that help individuals navigate life’s challenges.

Economic security also plays an important role, with the ability to manage monthly expenses and financial restrictions on daily activities emerging as significant material factors. These economic indicators are closely linked to financial stability, where financial insecurity can lead to stress and limit access to essential goods and services necessary for a decent standard of living.

Social exclusion is another critical factor, with its strong impact in the permutation analysis reinforcing the importance of belonging and community integration, particularly for older adults. Feelings of exclusion can severely affect mental health, increasing the risk of isolation and depression.

Age and its perceived impact on daily activities, along with marital status (e.g., widowhood), also significantly influence well-being. These variables reflect age-related challenges such as the loss of a life partner, reduced mobility, and diminished social resources, all of which can negatively affect overall well-being.

The value of permutation importance analysis in statistical modeling is evident, as it allows for the identification and prioritization of the most influential well-being factors. This method not only strengthens the model’s robustness but also provides valuable insights for targeted interventions and policy development aimed at supporting older adults. The comparable performance of Lasso and Ridge regression models suggests that the identified influential variables are both essential and stable across different regularization techniques. Recognizing and addressing these key factors is fundamental for advancing research and practical applications in subjective well-being studies.

Figure 2: Permutation importance - Lasso and Ridge models

Source: Graph based on SHARE w7-8-9

Figure 3 illustrates the pseudo-partial effects of variables included in the Lasso and Ridge regression models, revealing each variable’s contribution to subjective well-being. These effects reflect the isolated impact of each predictor, adjusting for the presence of other variables, making them a valuable tool for understanding how individual factors influence well-being.

Age emerged as the most significant positive factor in both models, suggesting that as people grow older, they may experience an increase in subjective well-being. This could be attributed to improved adaptation to life circumstances or greater acceptance of their conditions. Similarly, the perceived impact of aging on daily activities was significant, indicating that how individuals view their aging process directly influences their well-being.

Financial security also played an important role, with the ability to manage household expenses until the end of the month showing a strong positive effect. Effectively managing financial resources reduces stress and anxiety, fostering a sense of stability and comfort. Social integration was another key factor, as a reduced sense of exclusion was associated with higher well-being, emphasizing the importance of belonging and social connections.

Conversely, depression had a strong negative impact, reinforcing the critical role of mental health in well-being. Severe depression can impair daily functioning and diminish overall life satisfaction. Physical and health-related limitations also negatively affected well-being, as reduced mobility and autonomy can hinder an active and fulfilling lifestyle.

Figure 3: Pseudo-partial effects - Lasso and Ridge models

Source: Graph based on SHARE w7-8-9

Long-term health issues leading to disability further restricted participation in social activities and active living, demonstrating their detrimental effect on well-being. Additionally, being married but living separately from a spouse was associated with lower well-being, potentially due to emotional distress, relationship difficulties, or social isolation.

A notable difference between the models was that Lasso tended to emphasize variables with positive effects, whereas Ridge applied a more uniform penalty, leading to a more balanced distribution of variable importance. This difference explains why negative influences, such as depression and physical limitations, appeared more prominently in the Ridge model.

The combined use of permutation importance and pseudo-partial effects provides a comprehensive understanding of subjective well-being determinants. Permutation importance evaluates the model's sensitivity to variable perturbations, highlighting critical predictors such as mental health (Euro-D scale) and social support (social network satisfaction). Financial factors, including income management and financial constraints, were also identified as key areas for intervention and policy development.

On the other hand, pseudo-partial effects offer insights into how each variable contributes individually to well-being while controlling for the influence of other factors. Positive contributors, such as aging and financial stability, contrast with strong negative influences like physical limitations and chronic health conditions.

While these two analytical techniques assess variable importance from different perspectives, they complement each other in enhancing the understanding of well-being determinants. Together, they validate model

robustness and provide guidance for targeted interventions and policy development. These findings highlight variables that warrant further research and inform future policies aimed at improving subjective well-being.

The introduction of the Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) in this study represents a significant advancement in analyzing the factors that shape the subjective well-being of older adults in Europe. After an in-depth exploration of variable relationships through Lasso and Ridge regression models, transitioning to GBM marks a shift toward machine learning techniques that offer greater flexibility in modeling nonlinear effects and complex interactions. Unlike traditional regression methods, GBM iteratively refines predictions by learning from previous errors, making it particularly effective in capturing subtle influences that may be overlooked by linear models.

The results obtained through GBM (Figure 4) confirm the findings of the regression analyses, reinforcing the critical role of mental health in subjective well-being. Depression, as measured by the Euro-D scale, emerged as one of the most significant determinants, emphasizing the necessity of improving access to mental health care for older adults. Additionally, social exclusion was identified as a key negative factor, highlighting the profound impact of isolation and marginalization on well-being.

Figure 4: Hierarchy of factors' contribution to well-being subjective well-being determined by Gradient Boosting

Source: Graph based on SHARE w7-8-9

Financial security also proved essential, with the ability to manage household income until the end of the month ranking among the top predictors of well-being. Economic stability alleviates stress, enabling individuals to maintain a positive outlook on life. These findings underscore the need for strong financial assistance programs and pension systems that ensure older adults can sustain a comfortable and worry-free standard of living.

Physical health limitations were another significant influence, reinforcing the importance of accessible healthcare services and tailored physical activity programs that cater to the specific needs of the elderly population. Interestingly, residential location (urban vs. rural) did not play a major role, suggesting that while housing conditions might affect access to services, they are not primary determinants of subjective well-being in this context.

To better understand the true dependencies within the GBM model, a permutation importance analysis (Figure 5) was conducted. The results closely aligned with those from Lasso and Ridge regression, confirming that social and psychological factors, such as depression and social network satisfaction, play a dominant role. However, unlike regression models, which prioritized economic factors after social and psychological determinants, GBM emphasized social exclusion as a more influential predictor, reaffirming the necessity of social integration for well-being.

Figure 5: Permutation importance - GBoost model

Source: Graph based on SHARE w7-8-9

Beyond social and psychological determinants, economic factors, such as income management and financial constraints, were also highlighted as key predictors. Interestingly, GBM assigned greater importance to marital status, particularly widowhood, while Lasso and Ridge tended to emphasize age as a primary determinant. Furthermore, GBM reinforced the significance of health status and personality traits, particularly extraversion and neuroticism, while again confirming that residential location had a negligible influence on well-being.

Moving beyond permutation importance, the pseudo-partial effects analysis (Figure 6) provided insights into the isolated impact of each variable while controlling for interactions with other predictors. One of the most striking findings was the strong positive impact of social network satisfaction, reinforcing the role of social connections and community support in fostering well-being.

Figure 6. Pseudo-partial effects - GBoost model

Source: Graph based on SHARE w7-8-9

Conversely, being married but living separately had a notable negative effect, due to the lack of direct emotional support. Other negative influences included unemployment and poor self-rated health, further highlighting the importance of economic security and physical health in shaping well-being.

Among the positive predictors, being female and being a homemaker were associated with higher well-being levels. While gender disparities persist, certain aspects of women's life experiences may contribute to an enhanced perception of well-being. Similarly, being a homemaker positively influenced well-being, suggesting that the absence of occupational stress and the ability to focus on personal or family activities contribute to a better quality of life.

Comparing pseudo-partial effects across GBM and regression models, the direction of the effects remained consistent, though the magnitude varied. This difference stems from how each model processes data and captures complex variable relationships. While Lasso and Ridge simplify and regularize variables, GBM captures nonlinear interactions and intricate dependencies, explaining why the effect sizes differ while maintaining similar trends.

Overall, GBM provides a more refined and flexible approach to understanding subjective well-being, shedding light on the interplay between mental health, social support, financial security, and physical health. While regression models validate these factors' significance, GBM deepens the analysis, uncovering subtle interactions and dependencies that offer valuable insights for policymakers and practitioners.

By integrating findings from permutation importance and pseudo-partial effects, this study highlights the key areas requiring intervention to enhance older adults' well-being. The emphasis on mental health, social inclusion, financial stability, and healthcare access provides a solid foundation for policy recommendations aimed at fostering a supportive environment for positive and fulfilling aging experiences at both national and European levels.

5. Discussion & conclusions

This study applied multiple methodologies to establish a hierarchy of the most influential factors affecting the subjective well-being of older adults in Europe. By examining a range of variables—including physical and mental health, social support, and financial security—the analysis provided a broad perspective on the conditions that contribute to a positive aging experience.

Findings indicate that mental health, social support, and financial security are the main components shaping well-being in this demographic. Mental health emerged as the most significant factor, with all three models—Lasso, Ridge, and Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM)—showing its strong impact. While previous studies recognize mental health as an important determinant of well-being, it has not always been identified as the most decisive. However, this study suggests that for older adults, mental health plays a central role, highlighting the importance of mental health interventions in strategies designed to support well-being.

Social support also has a notable influence, with evidence showing that active engagement in social activities improves well-being. As people age, social networks may shrink due to the loss of friends or a life partner, which can have a negative impact. Maintaining social connections through community participation, senior clubs, and other engagement opportunities may help counteract this decline and contribute to a stronger sense of well-being.

Financial security also plays a key role, in line with research on the link between low income and reduced well-being in older adults. Those who struggle to cover basic expenses are more likely to experience psychological distress and lower life satisfaction. The ability to manage financial resources effectively supports a more stable and less stressful life, pointing to the importance of well-structured pension systems and financial assistance programs that help seniors maintain independence and dignity.

Interestingly, age itself had a positive effect on well-being, challenging traditional views that link aging with decline. This suggests that many older adults experience an increase in well-being over time, possibly due to better adaptation and acceptance of life circumstances. These findings highlight the importance of recognizing aging as a process that can involve personal growth and resilience rather than being solely associated with difficulties.

The comparison between GBM and linear regression models (Lasso and Ridge) shows how different analytical methods can reveal various aspects of the same issue. While Lasso and Ridge identified financial management and social exclusion as key factors, GBM provided a more detailed view of how these variables interact with others. This highlights the benefits of using multiple analytical techniques to develop a more complete understanding of well-being determinants.

By combining machine learning techniques with traditional regression models, this study builds on previous research while offering new perspectives on the relationships between psychological, social, and financial factors affecting older adults. The use of permutation importance techniques further clarified these relationships, allowing for the ranking of variables based on their influence on life satisfaction.

Through permutation importance analysis, this study identified mental health—specifically depressive symptoms—as the most significant factor influencing subjective well-being among older adults in Europe. This

reinforces previous findings while pointing to the need for better mental health services and policies to support aging populations.

Additionally, this research reassesses the core elements of well-being in older adults, placing mental health, social support, and financial security at the center. This revised perspective offers a clearer understanding of the specific needs of older adults, emphasizing the importance of targeted policies and interventions.

The findings also confirm the role of adaptation in aging as a key aspect of well-being. The positive impact of age on well-being suggests that efforts to promote resilience and adjustment should be central to aging policies. A comprehensive approach that addresses mental health, social engagement, and financial stability may support healthy and active aging.

The use of permutation importance allowed for a clear ranking of influential factors, with mental health—particularly depression—emerging as the strongest predictor of well-being in older adults across Europe. This finding suggests that policies and interventions should place a stronger focus on mental health care and emotional well-being in aging populations. Recognizing mental health as a major factor affecting well-being is essential not only for individuals but also for reducing the broader social and economic burden related to healthcare and support services.

Improving mental health among older adults may also help address the challenges of an aging society, a growing issue across Europe. The findings of this study highlight the need for a well-rounded approach to well-being, ensuring that older adults not only live longer but also experience a better quality of life.

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